

PREDICTIVE AND AUTOMATED METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE OPTIMIZATION OF RESIDENTIAL ENERGY CONSUMPTION

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ABSTRACT: *The energy consumption of the residential sector is experiencing rapid growth driven by urbanization, population increase, and rising living standards, resulting in economic and environmental pressures. This study proposes an innovative approach for residential energy optimization by combining the analysis of national policies, the review of international practices, and the development of a hybrid predictive model. The methodology is based on the statistical analysis of data from 80 households in Algeria, integrating building characteristics, occupant behaviors, and climatic variables. Forecasts generated by this model guide an automated management system capable of adjusting heating, lighting, and air conditioning in real time, aiming to enhance both energy efficiency and occupant comfort. This conceptual framework, flexible and reproducible, provides a methodological strategy applicable to various geographical contexts, contributing to energy planning and the reduction of environmental impacts.*

KEYWORDS: *energy optimization, residential sector, Algeria, predictive modeling, automated management, energy policies.*

1 INTRODUCTION

The global increase in energy demand, driven by industrialization and population growth, places considerable pressure on natural resources and contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions [1]. The residential sector, in particular, represents a major final energy consumer, accounting for nearly 47% in Algeria according to APRUE [2]. For countries like Algeria, where the economy relies heavily on hydrocarbon revenues, controlling household energy consumption is essential for both energy security and economic sustainability.

This article aims to examine international approaches for reducing energy consumption in residential buildings, analyze Algeria's national energy framework based on historical consumption trends, regulatory measures, and government programs, and identify the main challenges while

proposing a conceptual model for optimizing energy use in the Algerian residential sector.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies have explored residential energy consumption and optimization strategies, focusing on building performance, economic factors, and advanced modeling tools. These works provide a solid framework for analyzing the determinants of energy demand and methods for improving efficiency.

Chiara Lodi et al. [3] demonstrated that simple energy performance indicators can identify critical buildings and guide interventions for heating and cooling, despite the diversity in building age and usage.

Bouznit et al. [4] showed, for Algeria, an “inverted N” relationship between GDP per capita and residential electricity consumption, highlighting the role of efficient appliances and renewable energy sources.

Soo-Jin Lee et al. [5] and Daniel et al. [6] used regression and EnergyPlus to predict household consumption, revealing variable error margins and contrasting impacts on gas and electricity depending on climate scenarios. Mahsa Nazariye et al. [7] combined clustering and decision trees to classify English dwellings, showing the importance of insulation and boiler modernization.

Seyed Azad et al. [8] and Rezvan and Melissa [9] confirmed the relevance of machine learning models and random forests for anticipating future consumption and energy needs of buildings, with projections extending to 2080.

Yaolin Lin et al. [10] demonstrated the superiority of neural networks for residential prediction, while Khadidja Rahmani et al. [11] emphasized the role of hybrid energy sources in building retrofits in Algeria. Benjamin and Hamidreza [12] combined Energy Plus and Python with Bayesian and genetic optimization to create a high-performance energy model.

Taileb et al. [13] evaluated interventions such as triple glazing, reducing gas consumption by 34–38%. Guo et al. [14] proposed the REEDA method to estimate electricity consumption in Japan with a 14.4% error. Felix et al. [15] demonstrated the effectiveness of AutoML for predicting demand in public buildings.

Zaidi et al. [16] used digital twins to optimize urban energy consumption in Bertam, achieving a potential savings of 37%. Jinrong et al. [17] compared machine learning methods for predicting energy consumption in four building types, highlighting the superiority of XGBoost and the major influence of temporal variable.

Tahir Mahmood and Muhammad Asif (2024) [18] applied supervised learning to predict energy efficiency in Saudi Arabia. Guimei Wang et al. (2024) [19] combined conventional neural networks with evolutionary algorithms to improve predictions. Finally, Xue Cui et al. (2024) [20] used LightGBM and CatBoost to predict energy consumption in houses and apartments in the United States.

3 RESIDENTIAL ENERGY PROFILE IN ALGERIA

3.1 Evolution of the Energy Situation in Algeria Since 1962

Between 1980 and 2021, total energy consumption increased significantly, rising from 8.5 Mtoe to 50.2 Mtoe. This growth was mainly driven by the expansion of the residential and transportation sectors, while industry and construction progressed more moderately. The decline observed in 2020 (-7.7%) reflects the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, followed by a general recovery in 2021, illustrating the influence of economic development, urbanization, and infrastructure evolution on energy demand [21].

Fig. 1 Evolution of final energy consumption by sector between 1980 and 2021.

3.2 National Electricity Consumption in the Residential Sector

Between 1980 and 2021, residential electricity consumption in Algeria experienced significant variations. After moderate growth during the 1980s, it accelerated in the 1990s and 2000s, with annual rates of 7–8%, driven by urbanization, rising living standards, and the increased use of household appliances. Since 2010, growth has slowed to 4–5% per year, thanks to energy efficiency policies and the diversification of energy sources. The COVID-19 pandemic temporarily slowed this trend in 2020, followed by a slight recovery in 2021, illustrating the impact of policies, economic fluctuations, and global crises on residential consumption [22–28].

Fig.2 Evolution of Final Energy Consumption by Sector Between 1980 And 2022.

3.3 Energy Policy Strategies in Algeria

Table 1. National Energy Regulatory Framework

Law / Decree / Year	Objectives and main measures	References
Law n° 99-09 (1999)	Legal frameworks to manage energy, optimize consumption, and promote renewable energies.	[29]
Law n° 02-01 (2002)	Regulate electricity and gas, ensure safety and quality, and promote energy efficiency.	[30]
Law n° 04-09 (2004)	Promote renewable energies and monitor their implementation.	[31]
Decree n° 2000-90 (2000)	Regulate the thermal standards of new buildings to improve energy efficiency.	[32]
Executive Decree n° 04-149 (2004)	Launch the National Energy Management Program (PNME) to coordinate and monitor energy efficiency actions.	[33]
Executive Decree n° 15-69 (2015)	Certify renewable energy and encourage investments in the sector.	[34]
Interministerial Order of February 21, 200	Two orders from 2008 and 2009 established labeling and energy efficiency standards for domestic refrigerators and freezers.	[35,36]

4 METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted in this study is based on the use of real data from 80 households located in different climatic zones. The objective is to develop a robust predictive model capable of estimating residential energy demand and preparing its integration into an automated energy management system.

The collected data include:

- Actual electricity consumption, recorded quarterly,

- Building characteristics (living area, age, type of insulation, construction materials),
- Occupant profiles (number of inhabitants, occupancy schedules, usage behaviors),
- Climatic parameters, including solar irradiation, outdoor temperature, relative humidity, and seasonal variations.

These variables represent key factors that directly influence household energy needs and allow for training more reliable predictive models.

To identify the most performant model, several machine learning algorithms are tested and compared:

Random Forest Regression (RF): Systematic hyperparameter optimization is performed using GridSearchCV. This method explores different tree depths, subsample sizes, and splitting criteria to enhance model stability and accuracy.

XGBoost: A boosting-based algorithm known for its ability to handle complex interactions between variables and provide excellent performance on time series and tabular data.

Multilayer Perceptron (MLP): Part of the artificial neural network family, used to capture nonlinear relationships between consumption and explanatory variables. Different architectures (number of hidden layers, number of neurons, activation functions) are evaluated to optimize learning.

Model performance is evaluated using three complementary indicators:

- **Coefficient of Determination (R^2):** Measures the model's ability to explain consumption variability,
- **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):** Estimates the average deviation between predicted and actual values,
- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** More sensitive to small deviations and useful for model comparisons.

All data processing, training, and model validation are conducted in Python, using specialized libraries such as scikit-learn, XGBoost, and Tensor Flow/Keras. This approach ensures high flexibility, facilitates automated testing, and enables smooth integration of the final model into a PLC-controlled energy management system. The ultimate goal is to obtain a reliable predictive model capable of powering a real-time intelligent device for optimizing electrical loads.

5 ENERGY MANAGEMENT IN RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

Energy management in residential buildings refers to the intelligent organization and control of electrical equipment with the objective of reducing energy consumption, minimizing operational costs, and maintaining adequate comfort for occupants. In the proposed framework, the electrical demand of each

household is forecasted using machine learning models currently under evaluation—namely Random Forest Regression with Grid Search optimization, XGBoost, and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). The model achieving the highest predictive performance is then used to support the automated scheduling of residential electrical loads.

The management strategy is based on a dynamic adaptation of equipment operation according to four predefined modes, each corresponding to a specific predicted consumption level:

- **Mode 1 – Standard Consumption**
All essential and non-essential appliances operate normally. No restrictions or delays are applied, as the predicted demand remains within acceptable limits.
- **Mode 2 – Moderate Consumption**
Only critical loads such as lighting, refrigeration, and heating/cooling remain fully powered. Secondary appliances can be delayed, reduced, or rescheduled depending on the forecasted consumption profile generated by the predictive model.
- **Mode 3 – High or Peak Consumption**
Under predicted high-load conditions, only priority appliances are maintained. Non-essential equipment is temporarily switched off or shifted to prevent overload peaks and ensure better system stability.
- **Mode 4 – Economic Optimization**
Flexible appliances are scheduled according to time-of-use tariffs or periods of lower grid demand. This mode aims to reduce electricity bills without impacting the comfort of residents.

This adaptive and intelligent management mechanism combines real consumption data, predictive modeling, and load prioritization to optimize the overall energy performance of residential buildings. The flexibility of this framework allows it to be deployed in various household configurations and easily integrated into automated systems controlled by programmable logic controllers (PLCs).

5.1 Proposed Architecture of the intelligent PLC

In the context of implementing an intelligent energy management system, automation plays a central role in ensuring continuity between the predictive model and its operational execution. Embedded systems, particularly Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs), provide a robust solution for real-time management decisions. Their deterministic architecture, resistance to disturbances, and ability to handle multiple inputs/outputs make them well-suited for residential environments subject to rapid load variations.

However, integrating a machine learning model into a physical system presents several challenges, notably the synchronization between numerical forecasts, classification thresholds, and the embedded control logic. To evaluate this critical phase, a series of validation and behavior visualization tests of the control system was conducted in the ISIS (Proteus) simulation environment. This platform allowed reproducing the PLC operation, verifying the consistency of output signals generated by the management logic, and observing the real-time response of the virtual electronic circuit.

The simulations performed in ISIS were then compared with an initial hardware version of the PLC module, also presented in the article. This dual approach—numerical simulation followed by physical prototyping—confirms the compatibility between the predictive model and the control architecture while identifying necessary adjustments prior to real-world integration. This methodology strengthens the technical robustness of the proposed system and represents an essential step for its deployment in an operational residential environment.

Fig. 3 Program Testing on ISIS.

Fig. 4 Preliminary Control System Overview.

5.2 Flowchart of The Energy Management Strategy in The Residential Sector

The flowchart represents the overall decision-making architecture of the proposed energy management strategy for residential buildings. It provides a visual and structured depiction of the sequential operations that connect data acquisition, predictive modeling, energy-state classification, and automated load control.

The diagram begins with the collection and preprocessing of real consumption and environmental data. These inputs are then fed into the predictive modeling block, where several machine learning algorithms are evaluated. The selected model generates short-term demand forecasts, which are subsequently compared to predefined thresholds to determine the current energy state of the household.

The flowchart then branches into four possible management modes—normal, moderate, critical, and economic—each associated with a specific operating policy for electrical devices. These policies define how essential loads, secondary appliances, and flexible equipment are prioritized, shifted, or constrained.

By outlining the system's workflow from data input to automated decision output, the flowchart clarifies the internal logic of the proposed

framework and supports its implementation in a PLC-based automated control system.

Fig. 5 Flowchart of the Residential Energy Management Strategy

6 CONCLUSION

Energy consumption continues to rise, particularly in the residential sector. International literature highlights multiple technological, regulatory, and behavioral solutions that Algeria can adopt.

Analysis of national policies reveals significant efforts but also persistent challenges due to infrastructure limitations and subsidized energy prices.

Optimizing residential energy consumption can substantially reduce demand, improve energy

security, and support the national energy transition.

Future work should focus on integrating predictive models with smart metering systems to develop real-time energy management solutions.

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